

EXPERIMENTAL WORK ON THE INTEGRATION OF TECHNICAL AND ARTISTIC SCIENCES AND SYNERGETIC COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

The source argues that the integration of disciplines based on a synergetic approach is organized in the educational process based on the principles of systematization, interaction, and self-development. The study proposed methods for developing integrative lesson models, problem-based learning, and a methodology combining graphic and visual activities. The results of the experiment showed a significant increase in students' independent thinking, project activity, and creativity. Thus, the practical significance of this study in improving the training of personnel in the fields of fine arts, engineering graphics, architecture, and design is noted..

Introduction. In the modern education system, instead of teaching subjects separately, one of the important pedagogical tasks is to organize them based on mutual integration. In particular, the mutual integration of disciplines that combine technical and artistic fields, such as engineering graphics and fine arts, elevates student professional development to a qualitatively new level. Today, technical specialists are required not only to produce precise drawings and calculations but also to possess aesthetic thinking, creativity, and visual culture. Therefore, integrating teaching methods in engineering graphics and fine arts based on a synergistic approach is pedagogically relevant. A pilot study to improve student training in synergistic competencies through the mutual integration of technical and artistic disciplines was conducted at the Samarkand-Finnish Pedagogical Institute, Fergana State University, Chirchik State Pedagogical University, and Alfraganus University in the areas of fine arts, design, architecture, and engineering graphics. A total of 322 students from 12 groups participated in various stages of the pilot study. The main objective of the pilot study is to determine the impact of work aimed at improving the integration of teaching methods in engineering graphics and fine arts based on a synergistic approach to student learning on the quality of professional training of students in the fields of fine arts, design, architecture and engineering graphics.

The integration of engineering graphics and fine arts ensures:

- the harmonious development of spatial and artistic thinking;
- a combination of technical precision and aesthetic expressiveness;
- increased student creativity.

In the process of integration, concepts such as form, volume, perspective, proportion, light and shadow are studied as a single didactic block.

Synergetic competence is a person's ability to apply knowledge from different disciplines as a unified system. It includes the following components:

- knowledge integration;
- creative and critical thinking;
- complex problem solving;
- interdisciplinary knowledge transfer skills.

The teaching methods of fine arts and engineering graphics define the place of these subjects in the educational process, and the theoretical knowledge aimed at ensuring the professional training of future teachers includes the following:

* Providing theoretical knowledge about the essence, objectives, significance, and specific features of engineering graphics subjects, and in fine arts – about the essence, objectives, significance, and role of fine arts in society.

* Providing theoretical knowledge about the basic principles, methods, tools, and forms of teaching methods of fine arts and engineering graphics.

* Providing theoretical knowledge about modern pedagogical technologies used in the subjects of teaching methods of fine arts and engineering graphics.

* Providing theoretical knowledge about taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students in the subjects of teaching methods of fine arts and engineering graphics.

Engineering graphics occupies an important place in the system of technical disciplines, forming spatial imagination, constructive thinking and graphic culture in students. Through this discipline:

- analysis of geometric shapes;
- study of the laws of projection;
- skills in reading and compiling drawings are developed.

Visual presentation, sequence, logic and practical exercises are the guiding principles in the methodology of teaching engineering graphics.

The methodology of teaching fine arts is aimed at ensuring the artistic and aesthetic development of the individual, in which:

- painting,
- pencil drawing,
- composition,
- harmony of form and color

play a key role. Through this subject, students acquire not only the ability to depict, but also the aesthetic perception of the environment, figurative thinking and a creative approach.

The integration of engineering graphics and fine arts provides:

- the harmonious development of spatial and artistic thinking;
- the combination of technical accuracy and aesthetic expressiveness;
- increasing the creative activity of students.

In the process of integration, concepts such as shape, volume, perspective, proportion, light and shadow are studied as a common didactic unit.

In conclusion, the integration of fine arts and engineering graphics disciplines on the basis of a synergistic approach is an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. This approach allows students to develop not only technical knowledge and skills, but also artistic and aesthetic thinking, creative thinking and professional adaptability. The educational process, organized on the basis of the integration of engineering graphics and fine arts teaching methodologies, is highly effective in developing synergistic competence. This approach serves the comprehensive development of the professional training of future teachers and specialists. Therefore, in the future, it is an urgent task to widely introduce synergistic models and methodological recommendations for the integrative teaching of technical and artistic disciplines in the higher education system, improve curricula, and develop integrative competencies of teachers.

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